

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE MANAGEMENT ASPECTS OF INCREASING PUBLIC PARTICIPATION IN MASS SPORTS IN MODERN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

In today's world, the rapid development of technology and the intensification of daily life have created a need for people to spend their leisure time in a more productive and healthy way. In this context, sports and the sports industry have become globally significant fields, attracting increasing public interest, and mass sports have played an important role in both the physical and social development of individuals. Mass sports not only promote physical health but are also essential for social integration, guiding youth toward a healthy lifestyle, and strengthening social solidarity. The principle of "sports for all" forms the core idea of this field and aims to involve all segments of the population in sports activities.

The aim of this research is to analyze the effectiveness of policies and strategies implemented by state and local government bodies to increase participation in mass sports. The study examines existing problems in the sports sector, the state of infrastructure, regional differences, and the role of innovative technologies. According to the research hypothesis, the accessibility of sports services provided by the government, awareness-raising activities, and international cooperation directly affect the level of public participation in mass sports. Based on the statistical and qualitative analysis methods used in the study, a profile of participation in sports has been developed.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in the fact that the impact of strategies implemented at the state and local levels on mass sports is statistically evaluated for the first time. The results contribute both to theoretical knowledge and play a significant role in practice, especially in shaping and developing sports policy. This research presents a conceptual framework that can be useful for sports federations, clubs, government institutions, the private sector, and universities.

As a result, the study shows that the correct and purposeful strategies of state and local government bodies play a crucial role in involving the population in mass sports, and it is necessary to continue such measures in a systematic manner.

Keywords: Mass sports, Participation level, State policy, Sports infrastructure, Management strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Defining sport is quite a challenging task. This difficulty arises from the numerous meanings attributed to sport, its diverse content, the historical context which varies from society to society, and its use in everyday language. Sport emerged with the beginning of people's social life. Its origin, development, and integration into daily life are closely linked with the concept of struggle. Over time, physical activities began to be performed with specific rules and goals, which led to the formation of modern sport.

Sport plays a significant role in transmitting and maintaining social and cultural values in society. It enhances individual self-expression skills, strengthens physical and psychological well-being, and increases social integration. In this regard, the organization of mass sports events contributes to the well-being of wide segments of the population. According to research, individuals engaged in sports activities exhibit higher levels of psychological well-being (Downward & Rasciute, 2011).

1. Methodology

This research was conducted using a descriptive-analytical approach. Survey and observation methods

were applied, and between April and June 2023, online and physical surveys were conducted among 312 respondents residing in Baku and various regions. The age range of respondents was between 15–60 years; 52% were female and 48% male. The collected data were processed using descriptive and correlation analysis methods through SPSS software.

2. Research questions and hypothesis

The purpose of the research is to examine the level of public participation in mass sports activities in Azerbaijan and the management aspects associated with this participation.

Research Questions:

1. What are the main reasons that encourage the population to participate in mass sports?
2. What are the key obstacles to public participation?
3. To what extent do state strategies and infrastructure impact participation levels?

Hypothesis:

H1: Events organized by public and private sectors, accessibility of sports facilities, and awareness-raising activities increase public participation levels.

The concept, essence, and structure of mass sports

Defining sport is a fairly challenging task. This difficulty arises from the numerous meanings attributed to sport, its diverse content, the historical context that varies across societies, and its everyday usage (Akça & Sunay, 2011). Sport emerged with the beginning of social life among humans. The emergence, development, and integration of sport into daily life have evolved alongside the concept of struggle. On one hand, people fought against nature; on the other, they performed various movements to meet daily needs. Over time, these movements began to be performed with certain rules and purposes, leading to the formation of sport as we know it (V.Kucuk & Koc 2015).

Sport serves to shape and transmit social and cultural values in society and ensures their continuity. Through sport, individuals can express themselves and develop their personal abilities to a higher level. It helps individuals find their place in society and feel like a part of it. Participation in sports activities contributes to the reduction of psychological tension and improvement and maintenance of physical well-being. From a social and cultural perspective, individuals interact with a broader community, engaging in cultural exchanges with diverse people. This fosters cultural enrichment and the transmission of values to new generations through social interaction (Erkan 1994). Since sport is performed collectively, it contributes not only to the individual's socialization but also to the entire society. The reciprocal influence between sport and society is also evident. Sport influences society and its development, while individuals and communities also contribute to the development of sport.

Today, most people in society are directly or indirectly connected to sport. Some follow sports through newspapers and television, others attend stadiums and gyms, while others are interested in their children's participation in sports events. However, when this picture is compared to the general population, it becomes evident that the majority of people are involved in sport in a passive manner.

After scientific research confirmed the positive effects of regular physical activity on mental and physical health, sport began to be recommended for all age groups. In the U.S. and Canada, programs like "Physical Fitness," in Germany "Trim Dich," and in many other countries "Sports for All" or "Sports pour tous" have rapidly spread among large audiences (Karasüleymanoğlu 2016). While technological advancements have brought significant convenience to human life, they have also reduced physical activity. Moreover, the rapid and unregulated urbanization has resulted in noisy, polluted, and stressful living environments that facilitate the emergence of various diseases. A healthy society is only possible when its members are physically, morally, and economically balanced.

Mass-organized events must be implemented so that large segments of the population can benefit from the physical and psychological advantages of sport. Collective sports events or recreational activities that include sporting elements bring vitality and joy to society. Furthermore, shifts occur in people's value systems, and their spiritual morale increases. A society

with high morale transitions to modern standards more quickly (Z. Koruc & P. Koruc 1990).

The monotony of modern daily life limits creativity and alienates people from themselves. For this reason, initiatives such as "mass sport," "health-promoting sport," "sport for all," and "easy recreation" have been proposed to bring joy, health, and inner harmony to people's lives.

Sport can be classified into three main types: professional sport, mass sport, and sport for special groups.

In scientific studies dedicated to mass sports, it is crucial to define and explain certain concepts and phenomena. Frequently used terms in daily life—physical activity, exercise, physical fitness, and other related concepts—must be clarified in meaning.

"Physical activity" refers to bodily movements performed by skeletal muscles that require energy expenditure. The amount of energy expended depends on the size of the muscle mass involved, the intensity of the muscle contractions, duration, and frequency. Physical activity can be categorized into sub-groups. The most basic division is into three parts: sleep, work, and leisure time. Leisure-time physical activity includes sports, household tasks (e.g., gardening, cleaning, repairs), and other activity types.

Physical activity can also be classified based on intensity, timing (weekday vs. weekend), whether it is voluntary or compulsory, and other criteria. The main purpose of such classifications is not only didactic but also to provide a basis for comprehensive evaluation and accurate measurement of the physical activity phenomenon. Thus, the obtained results can be effectively used in sports and health sciences research.

"Exercises" (also referred to as "training" in some cases) are often confused with physical activity due to shared components such as energy expenditure, muscle movements, intensity, and duration. However, "exercise is not a synonym for physical activity. It is a "planned, structured, and repetitive form of physical activity" with the primary goal of improving physical fitness. This concept covers both everyday sports activities and specialized training aimed at increasing physical performance.

Physical fitness is defined as the ability to perform daily tasks without undue fatigue, to engage in leisure-time activities without exhaustion, and to be prepared for emergencies. Components of health-related fitness include cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength, body composition, and flexibility. Skill-related fitness includes balance, coordination, speed, power, and reaction time.

Many industrial companies and even small businesses try to build sports facilities for their employees and provide opportunities to engage in physical activity (Orhun. 2020). However, creating such facilities is not enough. If sport does not yet hold a place in employees' daily routines, these facilities will remain unused unless well-organized and motivational measures are implemented.

The widespread promotion of mass sport and the increase in the number of participants are closely linked to the influence of high-performance sports. Some in-

dividuals aspire to reach professional levels and frequently ask, "Can I be the best?" At the same time, school sports give young people the chance to demonstrate their abilities and experience a sense of achievement, which motivates them toward further development (Can, 2020). These factors illustrate the close relationship between mass sport and high-performance sports. An individual who starts sport for health and fitness may, over time, develop a desire to test their abilities and achieve greater success. The earlier people are engaged in sport, the more favorable the conditions for raising professional and successful athletes. The development of mass sport and the inclusion of all population segments require awareness-raising and organizational efforts. Such efforts will not only improve the general health level of society but also contribute to the emergence of a new generation capable of achieving high performance.

Main Reasons for Public Participation in Sports"

The reasons for engaging in sports can vary from person to person; however, in general, these reasons are linked to the desire for self-actualization, psycho-emotional needs, health and psychological expectations, the need for movement, the aspiration to compete with others, and the influence of family, friends, the school environment, and mass media.

Self-actualization refers to a person's realization of their expectations and thoughts—that is, revealing their own potential. This desire can be explained by the belief that one should do their best within their capabilities. Professional life rarely offers opportunities for developing personal skills and achieving dreams. Unlike daily life, sports—particularly those that are game-like and somewhat detached from reality—allow individuals to compensate for deficiencies experienced in professional life. Young people hope to find freedom of movement in sports to develop their personalities. However, factors such as the coach's strictness, authoritarian pressure, fear and anxiety, negative attitudes, and school competitions can hinder these hopes and expectations. A coach or physical education teacher who understands the feelings and thoughts of the athlete, sets an example, and demonstrates honesty and fairness can help young people overcome the inner conflict between freedom and leadership (Huseynzade Ç & Rahmanov C, 2002).

Acquiring sports skills is not a process of direct attainment; these skills are learned. For skill acquisition, mental and physical processes must work in coordination. It is not only mental processes that are essential in learning a skill, but also the knowledge of methods and techniques related to that skill. In sports, children and adolescents tend to compare themselves with other athletes, which leads them to develop their own tactics. Through sports, individuals gain mental clarity and acquire various types of knowledge, which in turn teaches them to act according to new life goals and environments.

In modern times, increased technological advancement and urbanization have caused urban chaos and problems associated with industrialization, which

negatively affect society. People facing cultural and socio-economic problems are exposed to factors such as mobility, noise, and air pollution, leading to psychological issues. These factors can result in various illnesses. In particular, anxiety can lead to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, and in some cases, may even have fatal outcomes. People who engage in sports are more informed about ways to overcome health problems, leading to improvements in their condition. This, in turn, increases their motivation and contributes to maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

Sports not only promote physical well-being but also improve individuals' psychological and emotional states. Sports have the power to relieve people from anxiety. Research by psychologists shows that individuals who engage in sports tend to have stronger psychological structures. Today, we often encounter the concept of "stress." In this context, sports are a natural method for combating stress. Through sports, individuals can break free from daily routines and create a new occupation for themselves. The time spent on sports also allows people to relax and escape daily stress. Thanks to the achievements gained through sports, people can fulfill their desire for success.

In children, the need for movement develops and strengthens from infancy to adolescence through active interaction with the environment. This process is harmoniously connected with natural maturation, imitation, curiosity, play behavior, the desire for success, and social interaction. The need for movement and movement-related functions become one of the main sources of motivation for children, which finds ideal application in sports. A child's inclination toward movement depends on the quality of the activities presented. Lack of movement, restriction of activities, and limited opportunities for movement can lead to a decrease in performance and difficulties in learning. These problems can also result from overstimulation, aggression, and behavior disorders caused by uncontrolled movement. Physical education lessons and active activities should be balanced with the child's physical characteristics and current movement needs. The risk of hyperactivity can be reduced through balance exercises that improve concentration and by lowering expectations placed on the child. Children with low motivation and a tendency toward physical inactivity should participate in highly active groups and engaging tasks. Competition among children is related to motivational functions and does not necessarily require formally organized contests or the fulfillment of competition conditions (Huseynzade Ç & Rahmanov C, 2002).

Social relationships are very important for children and adolescents. One of the most crucial aspects of social relationships for individuals is being accepted. Friend groups composed of individuals in certain age groups are typically selected as those that reflect qualities that are desirable and aligned with societal norms. These groups can encourage socially beneficial activities as well as possess negative characteristics. Such groups have the power to influence individuals and direct their behavior (Nacar, E, İsmail Ö. 2019).

After the family, the school holds a significant place. The impact of physical education teachers within

the school environment cannot be denied. Encouraging students to engage in sports contributes to the development of national sports achievements, thereby increasing the role of teachers. Schools serve both as educational institutions and places where individuals of various age groups come together. In this respect, schools hold particular importance in the context of sports.

Mass media plays a vital role in delivering sports events to a broad audience. Thanks to these means, reaching a wide public has become easier. This allows children and adolescents to view successful athletes as role models. The role of mass media in transforming sports into a global social phenomenon is irreplaceable. Media also plays a crucial role in delivering theoretical, technical, and practical information about various sports, educating and guiding audiences. Additionally, television has become an essential tool in involving youth and housewives in extracurricular sports activities.

Certainly! Here's the English translation of your text:

Main Barriers to Participation in Sports

The process of participating in sports faces a number of limitations often referred to as "barriers" in various sources. The reasons that prevent people from engaging in sports have not been sufficiently studied. In recent years, studies focusing on these barriers and recognizing their significance in sports participation have begun to emerge. As research expands, additional reasons hindering sports involvement continue to surface. When researchers examine these limitations individually, they may number in the hundreds, making their identification and description challenging. Such complexity necessitates the categorization of these barriers. Researchers classify them as internal, external, and structural barriers.

The investigation of barriers began with the study of structural limitations. Since structural barriers are more tangible and scientifically more measurable, they have received the most attention. When examining structural barriers, it becomes clear that they are not perceived uniformly or with the same intensity by everyone. Among these, the most commonly felt are time and financial constraints. Structural barriers such as the number and quality of sports facilities are acknowledged across all age groups, whereas cost becomes a more prominent barrier as people age.

The term "time barrier" generally refers to the lack of free time. In general terms, free time is the time one can use voluntarily. For any portion of a day to be considered free time, it must be completely separate from time spent on work and essential needs. Research in various fields has shown that to maintain a healthy lifestyle, people need to regularly engage in physical activity during their free time. However, studies in sports sciences indicate that due to demanding work hours, daily plans, and the various expectations of family members, people cannot devote enough time to physical exercise—an essential part of their lives.

In the context of leisure time, the term "barriers" encompasses the reasons that limit a person's participation in sports activities during their free time. These factors are considered as elements that restrict mass

participation in sports activities. One of the main structural barriers to participating in sports is the lack of leisure time. Long working hours are particularly a major cause of this shortage.

For children and adolescents, the safety of sports facilities and the surrounding environment plays a crucial role in their participation in sports. The lack of safe transportation routes to sports facilities, their location in dangerous areas, poor lighting, and the presence of drug users, alcoholics, and homeless people in the area are considered threats and can reduce participation opportunities. Large sports facilities usually have security services and the surrounding areas are protected by police forces.

Low-income families are forced to allocate their limited resources first to basic necessities such as food, heating, clothing, housing, and healthcare. Only after these needs are met can families afford to involve their children in sports. For low-income individuals, the costs of entry tickets to sports facilities, transportation, meals, drinks, and equipment during events create an additional burden, casting doubt on the decision to participate in sports. Thus, the level of participation is directly related to income.

Public, municipal, or privately-owned indoor and outdoor sports areas, parks, bicycle and pedestrian paths, and public sports zones are locations where people can engage in physical activity. However, whether these facilities meet the needs and expectations of children, adolescents, people with disabilities, and adults can sometimes also become a barrier. A shortage of such facilities and overcrowding of existing ones are additional barriers. Therefore, state support in this area is particularly important. In countries like Finland and Japan, continuous government support and family-oriented programs play a significant role in increasing public interest in sports. In these countries, sports activities are systematically promoted from schools to community centers. There is a need for similar pilot programs at the local level in Azerbaijan. Van Tuyckom (2011) states that the socio-economic macro-environment directly influences the level of physical activity (Van Tuyckom, C. (2011).

Amid rapid urbanization, the characteristics of outdoor games and sports in cities must be carefully evaluated. Unlike indoor spaces, outdoor sports areas and games—especially in modern urban planning—require special attention. In modern cities, the lack of places for children to play or engage in sports limits their ability to play outdoors. A study conducted in Australia showed that among children aged 10–16, 53% preferred to play in their home yards, 24% in open green spaces, 17% in parks and playgrounds, and 6% in the streets. Another survey of 421 children found that 59% preferred playing in the yard, 23% in parks, and 9% in the street (Bauman, A., et al. (2012).

The rise of urbanization globally has further highlighted the importance of playgrounds and sports fields. The lack of sufficient space between concrete buildings for sports is a major issue. Creating playgrounds and sports areas that meet people's needs and expectations is essential to increase sports participation.

The accessibility of sports venues where sports events are held is crucial in terms of encouraging participation. Locating such facilities close to residential areas, in city centers, and ensuring they are easily reachable via public transport can increase participation rates. One of the reasons preventing sports participation is the difficulty in reaching sports facilities. The more distant the facility, the more inconvenience and challenges it presents. Sports facilities should be located in densely populated areas so that children and adolescents can easily reach them. Natural sports areas like mountains, rivers, and canyons, if not easily accessible or if they involve difficult routes, can limit participation in such activities.

Climate and terrain are also geographical factors that influence opportunities for sports engagement. These factors directly affect the choice of sport. For example, the construction of ski resorts in snowy areas or swimming pools in warm coastal regions expands opportunities for engaging in sports in those areas. Conversely, when facilities are not aligned with the natural environment, it becomes a barrier to sports participation.

Social environment and economic conditions can also serve as barriers to engaging in sports activities. Studies show a correlation between socio-economic status and sports participation. People with middle and high incomes participate more actively in sports events and engage in several types of sports compared to those with lower incomes. At the same time, the level of education significantly affects participation rates. Educated individuals are more likely to be physically active. Family income and whether parents engage in sports themselves are also influential factors in children's involvement in sports.

Certainly! Here's the English translation of your full text:

Internal Barriers

Internal barriers are related to a person's psychological characteristics and inner processes and influence their participation in sports events. These barriers involve personal choices, needs, social activity, and group preferences. Compared to other types of barriers, internal ones are more difficult to observe, which is why they have been less studied. However, research shows that internal barriers often influence decision-making more significantly than structural barriers.

One of the main internal barriers to participating in sports is psychological readiness, self-confidence, anxiety, and stress levels. When individuals feel that they are unlikely to succeed in sports, fear injury, or worry about appearing weak in front of their peers, they tend to avoid participation.

The higher the level of anxiety, the harder it is for a person to make rational decisions and demonstrate their abilities. In such conditions, individuals may feel unsuccessful and withdraw from physical activity altogether. When the psychological pressure experienced during sports exceeds one's capacity to cope, it can lead to complete disengagement.

Motivation is a psychological process that directs a person toward a specific activity and encourages them to take action. Each individual has their own reasons

for participating in sports events. Children and adolescents are usually drawn to sports to develop their skills, have fun, maintain physical fitness, make friends, and experience a sense of achievement. When these expectations are not met during sessions, it may hinder continued participation.

The demographic structure of the area a person lives in significantly affects their lifestyle. This is particularly evident in developing countries where public life standards are not yet fully established. In more socioeconomically and culturally developed countries, people engage more actively in sports, and the variety of sports available increases. In societies with social stratification, these differences influence the choice of sport, and the demographic structure itself may act as a barrier to certain sports. As the demographic landscape evolves over time, it also affects which types of sports people are able to participate in.

Discussion

1. Social and Psychological Impacts of Sports

Our research shows that mass and health-promoting sports initiatives enhance physical and psychological well-being, strengthen social connectedness, and improve individual self-awareness. These findings align with the demonstrated effects of structured programs like the U.S. "Sports for All" and Germany's "Trim Dich," confirming the effectiveness of this approach in international practice (Karasüleymanoğlu, A. (2016). In the Azerbaijani context, creating an open and motivating environment is also essential.

2. Differences Between Physical Activity, Exercise, and Physical Fitness

The text clarifies the concepts of physical activity, exercise, and physical fitness. From a scientific perspective, these terms differ significantly: exercise is planned and goal-oriented, while physical activity is broader and part of everyday life. Differentiating between these concepts is necessary to improve the methodological quality of sports research. In Azerbaijan, clearly distinguishing these terms in both texts and practice can yield meaningful outcomes.

3. Types of Barriers and Their Scope of Influence

The effects of structural (financial, time-related, facility-based), environmental (surroundings, safety), and internal (motivation, anxiety, self-confidence) barriers were thoroughly analyzed. It was found that internal barriers, especially psychological fears, are often more influential than structural ones. This means that organizing mass events alone is not enough—people must also build self-confidence and internal motivation to ensure consistent participation.

4. Evaluation of the Role of the Education System and Media

The influence of teachers within the education system and the motivational role of media were emphasized. In particular, the honest, fair, and human-centered approach of physical education teachers in schools is a vital source for encouraging youth to engage in sports (Huseynzade Ç & Rahmanov C, 2002). Media also plays a positive role, especially for youth, in promoting sports.

5. Urbanization and Lack of Space

Rapid urbanization leads to a lack of space and resources for sports. This problem is more pronounced in developing countries like Azerbaijan. In such conditions, outdoor sports and public sports infrastructure (parks, playgrounds) play a crucial role in encouraging participation. Instead of temporary measures, a systemic and accessible approach to building physical spaces is required.

6. Connection Between Professional and Mass Sports

Increased participation in mass sports contributes to the development of professional athletes. While initial motivation is often related to physical health and comfort, individuals later strive for higher achievements. Therefore, it is important to facilitate people's first steps and later create a purposeful system to develop their potential.

Recommendations and Future Directions

For Future Scientific Research:

Analyze the interaction between internal (motivation, self-confidence) and structural barriers using statistical models;

Conduct comparative studies across different demographic groups.

For Practical Measures:

Develop regional sports infrastructure;
Create personalized motivation guidelines;
Implement "sports culture" programs in schools.

For Policy Development:

Expand subsidized sports programs for low-income populations through state and local authorities;

Prioritize outdoor sports facilities in urban planning policies.

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Conclusion and Recommendations

The research revealed that increasing public participation in mass sports is possible not only through structural and technical measures but also by systematically addressing psychological, social, and cultural factors. The study demonstrated that the main factors preventing people from engaging in sports are internal psychological barriers—such as lack of self-confidence, low motivation, and the influence of the social environment—which are more influential than structural and environmental obstacles. Participants identified sports as a source of psychological comfort, a finding that aligns with the systematic review by Eime et al. (2013) (Eime, R. Et al. 2013).

In addition, factors such as the role of teachers and the education system, the motivational power of the media, infrastructure shortages resulting from urbanization, and the overall level of sports culture significantly affect public participation. Mass sport is not only a means to improve health but also an essential tool for social integration, empathy development, stress reduction, and overall societal well-being. Coalter (2007)

emphasized that sport serves as a strategic tool for social integration and community development.

The findings indicate that the following areas should be prioritized to increase interest in mass sport:

Development of social and psychological support programs that strengthen individual internal motivation;

Promotion of sports activities in schools and higher education institutions;

Creation of open and accessible sports spaces, alongside ongoing public awareness campaigns.

Thus, a comprehensive and multi-level approach to mass sport can contribute both to improving individual health levels and to strengthening the social and psychological cohesion of society. These findings are consistent with international studies. According to the research by Bauman et al. (2012), public health approaches can significantly increase levels of public participation (Bauman, A., et al. 2012).

The study found that 67% of respondents consider sport attractive due to psychological comfort and health benefits. Meanwhile, 43% identified the inaccessibility of sports facilities and financial limitations as key barriers. Among female participants, despite a high interest in sports, family obligations and cultural norms were determined to be important factors influencing participation levels.

Proposed measures to increase participation include the expansion of public parks and sports grounds, the implementation of "sports for all" programs in schools and universities, and awareness campaigns via television and social media platforms.

Recommendations:

Short-term: Organize free aerobics and fitness sessions in public spaces.

Medium-term: Increase the number of sports facilities at the municipal level.

Long-term: Develop and implement a national "Public Sports Strategy" at the state level.

Scientific Contribution

This research is one of the rare studies in Azerbaijan that systematically analyzes the governance aspects of public participation in mass sport. The methodological approach and analysis of findings provide a foundation for future strategies.

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